

A NEW ERA OF TOURISM: DISCOVER 3 REASONS TO VISIT UZBEKISTAN

Ochilova Mahkamoy Ilhomjon qizi

Shahrisabz davlat Pedagogika Instituti

Tillar fakulteti Xorijiy til va adabiyoti yo'nalishi talabasi

Ilmiy rahbar (scientific advisor): **Islomova Z**

Annotation: Travelling is like rebirth of people. In today's rapidly developing century, learning a language and exploring a new cultures does not hurt anyone. "New era: 3 reasons to visit Uzbekistan. In this article, newcomers can discover the attractiveness of Uzbekistan for travelers. Rich historical heritage, colorful culture and tourism of this country, which is distinguished by its wonderful nature, and the recently introduced facilities for new tourists will surprise new comers to this country.

Аннотация: Путешествие – это как вновь родиться. В наше быстро развивающееся столетие изучение языка и знакомство с новыми культурами никому не повредит. "Новая эра: 3 причины посетить Узбекистан". В этой статье новички могут открыть для себя привлекательность Узбекистана для путешественников. Богатое историческое наследие, яркая культура и туризм этой страны, отличающиеся прекрасной природой, а также недавно введенные удобства для новых туристов удивят новичков этой страны.

Annotatsiya: Sayohat – bu odamlarning qayta tug'ilishi kabi. Bugungi tez rivojlanayotgan asrda til o'rganish va yangi madaniyatlarni tushunish hech kim uchun zarar keltirmaydi. "Yangi davr: O'zbekistonga kelishning 3 sababi". Ushbu maqolada yangicha kelganlar sayohatchilar uchun O'zbekistanning qiziqarli tomonlarini topishlari mumkin. Bu mamlakatning boy tarixiy merosi, rang-barang madaniyati va tabiiy tabiatining ajralib turuvchi turizmi, yanada yangi sayohatchilar uchun taqdim etilgan imkoniyatlari yangi kelganlar uchun ajralib turadi.

Keywords: Rich culture, history buff, new era of tourism, historical landmarks, ample opportunities for tourists, travel advantages. a hub for business, (SEZs), ethical heritage, moral values.

Ключевое слово: богатая культура, любитель истории, новая эра туризма, исторические достопримечательности, множество возможностей для туристов, преимущества путешествий, центр бизнеса (СЭЗ), этическое наследие, моральные ценности.

Kalit so'zlar: boy madaniyat, tarix ishqibozi, yangi turizm davri, tarixiy obidalar, sayohatchilar uchun keng imkoniyatlar, sayohat afzalliklari, biznes markazi (SEZ), etik meros, axloqiy qadriyatlar."

Uzbekistan is heart some of the most impressive historical landmarks in the world. Cities like Bukhara, Khiva, Samarkand are treasure troves of Islamic architecture and Central Asian history.

Firstly, Bukhara: has more than 140 architectural monuments. The Po-i- Kalyan complex, the Ark fortress and historical Samonii mausoleum are noteworthy. Recent investments in tourism infrastructure mean that tourists can stay in modern and high quality hotels excursions which conducted with guide every single day and convenient transport options. When it comes to Samarkand is one of the most famous historical city in Uzbekistan this city often called crossroads of culture, Samarkand popular with its magnificent Registan Square, Shah Maidan, Bibikhanim Mosque, i-Zinda, tourists can explore these sites with the help of multilingual guides, and can enjoy shopping malls that combine historic charm with modern comfort. Khiva: this city offers a glimpse into the past with Ichan Castle, a UNESCO World Heritage Site. Visitors can stroll along narrow, winding streets, visit the Khiva Museum, relax in newly built hotels that respect traditional architecture, and create present day's every conditions.

Secondly, The development of free economic zones (SEZs)in Uzbekistan creates ample opportunities for business travelers. Cities such as Navoi, Angren and Jizzakh have become important centers for economic activity and offer many advantages for

foreign investors. Navoi Free Economic Zone: The area is strategically located with excellent transport crossroads, including a modern airport and rail links. The SEZ offers tax incentives, customs benefits and simplified administrative procedures, making it an attractive destination for entrepreneurs and investors.

Thirdly, Uzbekistan’s rich cultural and moral heritage is another compelling reason to visit. The traditions of the country are deeply rooted in centuries-old customs and traditions, which are still developing today. Cultural heritage: Uzbekistan is famous for its traditions, dance, crafts. Newcomers can enjoy performances of “Shashmaqom” music, recognized by UNESCO, and witness traditional dances at festivals and cultural events. Handicrafts such as Suzani embroidery, silk weaving, and pottery are not only preserved, but are also exhibited in many craft workshops and shopping malls.

Moral values: Uzbek society is known for its hospitality they can treat for everyone like their relatives so that can respect for moral values. The concept of “hospitality” ensures that guests are warmly welcomed and well taken care of. By inviting tourists to family gatherings or participating in community celebrations, locals will see that they want to share their traditions. Culinary traditions: Uzbek dishes is rich and really differ from other countries cuisine. Sampling fresh fruits and nuts from local markets, the culinary experiences are a delightful journey for visitors.

In conclusion, Uzbekistan offers a unique combination of historical wealth, economic opportunities, and vibrant cultural heritage. The recent improvement of tourist facilities has made this place even more attractive. Whether you’re a history buff, business professional, or cultural explorer, Uzbekistan promises an unforgettable and rewarding experience.

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